

Kuumbi Cave

also known as "Pango La Kuumbi"

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Entry tags: Archaeological Site, Religious Group, African Religions, African Religion, Religious Place, Swahili Religion, Kuumbi Cave, Cave or Cavern, Islam

Kuumbi Cave is a karst limestone cavern on the southeast coast of the island of Unguja (Zanzibar). It is sacred to the local community as a spirit ("shetani") is considered to inhabit the site. Like all caves in Zanzibar with a freshwater source, Kuumbi Cave has a spirit associated with it. The spirit is often associated with pythons and is venerated by the local community. The landscape around Kuumbi Cave is sacred as well. The cave is located in an East African Coastal Forest, an ecosystem which has disappeared from most of the island except around sacred caves and in national parks. The forest around Kuumbi Cave has been preserved because of religious strictures against cutting wood there. The local mganga (healer) conducts ceremonies at Kuumbi and other sacred caves. These rituals are secret for the most part and are conducted privately by the mganga, but what is known is that cloth and incense are used and offerings of food and drink are made to the spirit. There is also a tradition of tying strips of cloth to a wooden framework within the cave as offerings to the shetani. This latter practice is performed by lay visitors to the cave (i.e. not mganga), especially by students praying for good scores on their exams. The sacred practices associated with caves like Kuumbi are considered part of the intangible heritage of Zanzibar, but they are increasingly under threat from the tourist industry which seeks to monetize the caves by showing them to tourists and allowing them to swim in their sacred waters. Purchasers of caves often bar mgangas and others from performing rituals in the caves. Archaeologists have excavated Kuumbi Cave since the early 2000s, and have discovered evidence of human occupation of the cave dating to at least as far back at 17,000 years ago. However, the date of the origin of the sacred nature of the cave remains uncertain. The cave was occupied by hunter gatherers until the 20th century, when the cave was abandoned in favor of the nearby settlements of Jambiani and Makunduchi. There are stories associated with the most recent occupation of the cave by hunter gatherers. The first says that the cave was used by two lovers for their tryst. The water in the cave was discovered by accident when, post-coitus, the woman threw a stone to the back of the cave and heard a splash. The other story says that the cave was discovered by hunters when an antelope they were chasing with their dogs ran into the cave, which was at the time hidden behind vegetation. Archaeological evidence suggests that the hunter gatherers of Kuumbi were exploiting a broad range of fauna, including those no longer present on the island. While no longer the site of a living population, the cave remains sacred to people near and far.

Date Range: 1900 CE - 2023 CE

Region: Unguja Island

Region tags: Africa, Eastern Africa, Swahili

Unguja island showing the location of Kuumbi Cave and other archaeological sites

Status of Participants:

✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

General Variables

Sources and Excavations

Print Sources

Print sources used for understanding this subject:

- Source 1: Shipton, Ceri, et al. "Reinvestigation of Kuumbi Cave, Zanzibar, reveals later Stone Age coastal habitation, early Holocene abandonment and Iron Age reoccupation." *Azania: Archaeological Research in Africa* 51.2 (2016): 197-233.
- Source 2: Sinclair, Paul, Abdurahman Juma, and Felix A. Chami. "Excavations at Kuumbi Cave on Zanzibar in 2005." *Studies in the African past* 5 (2019).
- Source 3: Faulkner, Patrick, et al. "Long-term trends in terrestrial and marine invertebrate exploitation on the eastern African coast: Insights from Kuumbi Cave, Zanzibar." *The Journal of Island and Coastal Archaeology* 14.4 (2019): 479-514.

Has this place been the focus of excavation (pre-modern, illicit, or scientific):

Answer 'Yes' for each period or type of excavation.

– Yes

Type of excavation:

- Scientific

Years of excavation:

- Year range: 2002-2023

Name of excavation

- Official or descriptive name: Excavations by Felix Chami, The SEALINKS Project, Akshay Sarathi, and Maximillian Chami

Topographical Context

Is the place associated with a feature in the landscape

– Water source

– Cave

Notes: A fresh water spring lies at the back of the cave, shrouded in dim light. A spirit known as a "Shetani" is believed to reside at or near this pool.

– Elevation

– Tree, grove, or forest

Notes: The cave is located atop a hill and is accessible only by a footpath that passes through a forest. The forest is considered sacred and thus is not harvested. Along with Jozani Forest, the forest surrounding Kuumbi Cave is one of the last examples of the East African Coastal Forest ecosystem present on Zanzibar.

↳ Type of elevation

– Hill

Does the place involve human-made features besides structure:

Other features might be ground clearing, terracing, other modifications of the local environment.

– Yes

↳ Type of feature

– Clearing

– Trackway or road-surface

– Water feature

– Other [specify]: Archaeologist Felix Chami created concrete signposts describing what he found in each trench. These signposts look like podiums, with writing on the slanted top surface. The text on these signposts note what he discovered in a particular trench (marine shell, bone, human remains, etc.). The text is in English, which is surprising given that the language most familiar to locals is Kiswahili.

– Yes

↳ Type of feature

– Other [specify]: In 2023, graffitied names were found in the second, inner chamber of the cavern. This graffiti consists of names scratched into the limestone and a hand-stencil created with spray paint on a stalactite.

Is the place situated in an urban or significantly urbanized area:

– No

Is the place situated in a rural setting:

– Yes

↳ Are there settlements in close proximity to the place:

– Yes

Notes: The settlements of Jambiani and Makunduchi lie close by (5-10km from the cave). These are the settlements to which the descendants of the hunter-gatherers who lived in the cave moved sometime during the 20th century.

↳ Are there routes of travel in close proximity to the place:

– Yes

Notes: The cave is accessible by a footpath that climbs the hill, at the top of which is situated

the cave. The footpath in turn connects to a dirt road, which runs about 3km before linking up with the main road.

Is the place situated far removed from non-religious places of habitation:

– Yes

Notes: The cave is located about 5km as the crow flies from the nearest settlement (Jambiani)

Is there an established route of travel connecting it to a wider transportation network:

– Yes

Notes: The only way to access the cave is via a footpath that connects to a dirt road which in turn connects to a paved road that runs along the eastern coast of Unguja Island

Structures Present

Are there structures or features present:

Instructions: Answer once for each structure/feature or group that can be differentiated.

– Yes

A single structure

– No

One single feature

– Water channel

Notes: Rainwater flowing into the cave creates a water channel that digs into the sediment and carries water to the pool in the back of the cave

A group of structures:

– Yes

Notes: The only artificially constructed structures with the cave are the concrete signposts/podiums created by Felix Chami. They seem to have been built using a cinderblock core faced with cement or concrete.

Are they part of a single design/construction stage:

– Yes

A group of features:

– No

↳ Is it part of a larger place/sanctuary:

– No

Notes: That said, all caves with water (and some without water) are considered sacred on Zanzibar. It is unknown whether the hundreds of caves on Unguja and even on the northern island of Pemba are considered to interact with each other spiritually.

↳ What is the function of the structure/feature or group:

Answer "Yes" once for each distinct function

– Other [specify]: Archaeological markers built by Felix Chami, marking the location of his archaeological trenches and his finds

↳ Is the structure/feature finished:

– Yes

↳ Was the structure/feature intended to last beyond a generation:

– Yes

↳ Was the structure/feature modified through time:

– No

↳ Was the structure/feature destroyed:

– No

↳ Has the structure/feature been reconstructed:

– No

Reasons for Creation/Construction/Consecration

Is the place used for the worship of/communication with non-human supernatural beings:

– Yes

↳ Dedicated to a supernatural being:

– Yes [specify]: A Shetani or spirit is supposed to reside near the pool of water at the back of the cave, and is the focus of veneration by local healers known as mganga (pl. waganga). "Shetani" likely derives from the Arabic "shaitān", meaning "devil". It is possible that spirit veneration in the cave antedates Islamic practice on the island, which when it arrived branded local spirits/deities as devils. Interestingly, "shetani" does not carry the same connotations of devilishness as does "shaitān". It is possible that as the word was indigenized by the Swahili, it lost some of its pejorative meaning. The Shetani at Kuumbi is venerated with offerings of cloth, food and drink (including bottles of soda), and incense. Rituals take place in secret, and

possibly at night.

- ↳ Dedicated to more than one supernatural being:
 - No

Is the place used for the worship of a semi-divine human being:

– No

Is the place used for the worship of non-divine ancestors:

– Yes

Notes: The Shetani was identified by some with pythons and ancestors, but the strength of these connections remains unknown.

- ↳ Is it a cenotaph:
 - No

Notes: However, two human burials dating to ~500ya were discovered by Felix Chami in the cave. The individuals were buried one atop the other and covered by a cairn of stones.

- ↳ Does it commemorate a family/clan/group:
 - No

Was the place commissioned/built by an official political entity:

A political entity is a local power structure that leverages a workforce.

– No

Were the Structures built by specific groups of people:

– Yes

- ↳ Groups:
 - Other [specify]: Archaeologists

Was the place thought to have originated as the result of divine intervention:

– No

Was the place created to mark or commemorate the birthplace of a supernatural or human being:

– No

Was the place created as the result of an event:

– Yes

↳ Specify

– Other [specify]: There are stories associated with the most recent occupation of the cave by hunter gatherers. The first says that the cave was used by two lovers for their tryst. The water in the cave was discovered by accident when, post-coitus, the woman threw a stone to the back of the cave and heard a splash. The other story says that the cave was discovered by hunters when an antelope they were chasing with their dogs ran into the cave, which was at the time hidden behind vegetation. The cave was then occupied by hunter-gatherers, who abandoned it only in the 20th century.

Was the creation of the place sponsored by an external financial/material donation:

– No

Was the establishment of the place motivated by:

– Expectation of favor in return

Notes: Once the spirit was considered to reside in the cave, offerings began to be made in expectation of reward. This reward could be linked with divination and healing practices associated with the mganga (pl. waganga), who conduct rituals in the cave.

Was the place built specifically for housing scriptures/sacred texts:

– No

Design and Material Remains

Overall Structure

Is the place made up of multiple built structures:

– No

Notes: But there are some structures built by Felix Chami to mark his trenches, as described above.

Is monumental architecture present:

Monumental architecture is defined here as a built structure that surpasses average human proportions and in general is larger and more complex than is necessary to fulfill the structure's utilitarian function(s). Examples of monumental architecture include Mesopotamian Ziggurats, Egyptian Pyramids, Greek and Roman temples, Mesoamerican Pyramids, North American and Aegean burial mounds, etc.

– No

Is the structure/feature made out of natural materials:

Answer [Yes] for each material type

– No

Notes: Felix Chami's trench markers are made of concrete.

Is the structure/feature made out of human-made materials

– Yes [specify]: Concrete

Decoration

Is decoration present:

– Yes

Notes: In 2023, graffiti was discovered in the cave. This consists of people's names incised into the cave's limestone walls. A hand stencil made with spray paint was also found to decorate a stalactite. These decorations do not have any association with the rituals that are practiced in the cave.

↳ Is decoration part of the building (permanent):

– Yes

↳ On the outside:

– No

↳ On the inside:

– Yes

Notes: The graffiti is located on the far wall of the inner chamber of the cave.

↳ Is decoration attached to the building, i.e. movable reliefs or tapestries

– No

↳ Is the decoration figural:

A figural representation is defined here as one that contains the depiction of discernible human, anthropomorphic, animal, or zoomorphic forms. In general, it differentiates between animate and inanimate beings, as well as between narrative compositions and still life, landscapes, abstraction, etc. Answer [Yes] for each type of figure depicted

– Yes

↳ Are there gods depicted:

– No

↳ Are there other supernatural beings depicted:

– No

↳ Are there humans depicted:

– Yes

Notes: A human hand has been stenciled on a stalactite using black spray paint

↳ Are there animals depicted:

– No

↳ Are there animal-human hybrids depicted:

– No

↳ Is the decoration non-figural:

– Yes

↳ Is it geometric/abstract

– No

↳ Floral motifs

– No

↳ Is it writing/caligraphy

– Yes

Notes: Names have been graffitied onto the far walls of the cave's inner chamber.

↳ Other [Specify]

–Other [specify]: The graffiti consists of writing in addition to a stenciled hand print

↳ Is the decoration hidden or restricted from view:

– No

↳ Are there statues present:

– No

↳ Are there reliefs present:

A relief as opposed to sculpture carved on the round is a work of sculpture in which the figures project from a background support, generally a flat surface. Reliefs can be carved out of stone,

clay, or a similar material.

– No

↳ Are there paintings present:

– No

↳ Are there mosaics present:

– No

↳ Are there inscriptions as part of the decoration:

– Yes

↳ Are the inscriptions ornamental:

– Yes

Notes: Names have been graffitied on the back wall of the inner chamber of the cave

↳ Are the inscriptions informative/declarative

[e.g. historical narratives, calendars, donor lists etc...

– No

↳ Are the inscription a formal dedication:

– No

↳ Other [Specify]

–Other [specify]: The inscriptions are only graffitied, and do not have any association with the rituals performed at the cave. The graffitied names seem to relate to increasing amounts of tourist activity in the cave. Tourism hampers the ability of the local healer (mganga) to conduct their rituals

↳ Other type of decoration:

– No

Iconography

Are there distinct features in the places iconography:

– Yes

Notes: Incised names and a stenciled hand form part of the cave's "decoration".

↳ Eyes (stylized or not)

– No

↳ Supernatural beings (zoomorphic)

– No

↳ Supernatural beings (geomorphic)

– No

↳ Supernatural beings (anthropomorphic)

– No

↳ Supernatural beings (abstract)

– No

↳ Portrayals of afterlife

– No

↳ Aspects of doctrine (e.g. cross, trinity, Mithraic symbols)

– No

↳ Humans

– Yes

Notes: A human hand has been stenciled recently on a stalactite in the inner chamber of the cave.

↳ Supernatural narratives

– No

↳ Human narratives

– No

↳ Other [Specify]

– Other [specify]: Names have been incised into the limestone walls of the inner chamber of the cave

Beliefs and Practices

Funerary Associations

Is this place a tomb/burial:

– No

Is this a place for the worship of the dead:

– Yes

Notes: The spirit or Shetani believed to reside in the cave near the freshwater spring may be associated with pythons and/or ancestors. This remains uncertain.

For the worship of a deceased person(s):

– Yes

Notes: The Shetani or spirit could represent deceased ancestors or a python spirit, but this has yet to be verified

For the worship of a deified human:

– No

For the worship of a deceased hero:

– No

Is this a place for treatment of the corpse:

– No

Are co-sacrifices present in tomb/burial:

Co-sacrifices are animal/human sacrifices prompted by the death of the primary occupant of the tomb/burial.

– No

Are grave goods present:

– No

Are formal burials present:

– Yes

Notes: Two burials dating to ~500ya were discovered by archaeologist Felix Chami in the cave. These are likely associated with the hunter-gatherer populations that lived in the cave until the 20th century. Whether the burials indicate that the cave's sacred status is at least 500 years old remains uncertain, but they are at least suggestive of some mortuary significance of the cave. At present, no treatment of corpses or burials takes place in or near the cave.

↳ As cenotaphs:

– No

↳ In cemetery:

– No

↳ Family tomb/crypt:

– No

↳ Domestic context:

Interred beneath floors of house, or in areas of domestic activity

– No

↳ Other

–Other [specify]: Two individuals were discovered buried near the main entrance of the cave by archaeologist Felix Chami. The first burial was covered up and perhaps forgotten before the second burial was deposited atop the first. A cairn was then constructed over both burials. The cairn itself was covered by sediment, hiding it until it was excavated in 2003. The bodies have since been moved to facilities owned by the Revolutionary Government of Zanzibar. The bodies are likely associated with the hunter-gatherer populations that lived in the cave until recently.

Supernatural Beings

Is a supreme high god is present:

– No

Does the supreme high god communicate with the living at this place:

– No

Are previously human spirits present:

– I don't know

Notes: They may be present, as the spirit or Shetani that resides in the cave may have a link to the ancestor spirits of the communities close by,

Do human spirits communicate with the living at this place:

– I don't know

Notes: The Shetani, which may represent ancestors, could interact with humans in a variety of ways in the cave

Are nonhuman supernatural beings present:

– Yes

Notes: A spirit known as a "Shetani" is considered to live in the cave, especially around the area near the freshwater spring. That is where rituals to venerate this spirit take place.

↳ Nonhuman spirits can be seen:

– I don't know

↳ Nonhuman spirits can be physically felt:

– I don't know

Do nonhuman spirits communicate with the living at this place:

– Yes

Notes: But how this communication takes place is unknown. It is possible that sightings of pythons are seen as evidence for the manifestation of this spirit.

↳ In waking, everyday life:

– Yes

↳ In dreams:

– I don't know

↳ In trance possession:

– Yes

Notes: There are remote of possession cults centered around women in Zanzibar in the 19th and 20th centuries. The extent to which these cults influenced current practice of rituals at places like Kuumbi Cave remains unknown.

↳ Through divination practices:

– Yes

Notes: The mganga is a healer, but also conducts divination rituals. It is possible that divination rituals take place in Kuumbi Cave.

↳ Only through religious specialists:

– Yes

Notes: The mganga is the only person who conducts rituals at Kuumbi Cave, even though lay people regularly leave offerings for the spirit.

↳ Only through monarch:

– No

Other

–Other [specify]: None

Are mixed human-divine beings present:

– No

Notes: That said, it is possible that the Shetani is both an ancestor and connected to python spirits somehow.

Do mixed human-divine beings communicate with the living at this place:

– No

Is the supernatural being/high god present in the form of a cult statue(s):

– No

Supernatural Interactions

Is supernatural monitoring present:

– I don't know

Do visitors communicate with the gods or supernatural beings:

– Yes

Do visitors communicate with gods:

– No

Do visitors communicate with other supernatural beings:

– Yes

Notes: The mganga i said to contact and converse with the Shetani or spirit that lives in the cave

Ritual and Performance

Do rituals occur at this place:

Rituals are visibly enacted behaviors by one or more people for the purposes of religious observance.

– Yes

Notes: The mganga conducts rituals to venerate and contact the spirit or Shetani that lives in the cave

↳ Do large-scale rituals take place:

– No

↳ Do small-scale rituals take place:

– Yes

Notes: The mganga, either alone or with only a 1-2 helpers, conducts the ritual

↳ On average how many participants are present in large-scale rituals:

–specify: 1-5

Notes: No large-scale rituals take place at the cave

↳ How often do these rituals take place:

–specify: Weekly

↳ Are there orthodoxy checks:

– No

↳ Are there orthopraxy checks:

– I don't know

↳ Are there synchronic practices:

– I don't know

↳ Are there intoxicants used during the ritual:

– I don't know

Sacrifices, Offerings, and Maintenance

Are sacrifices performed at this place:

– Yes

Notes: Small animals like chickens are associated with sacrifices performed by the mganga. Incense, cloth, and foodstuffs also comprise offerings made to the spirit.

↳ Are there animal sacrifices:

–Yes [specify]: Small animals like chickens are sacrificed

↳ Are there human sacrifices:

– No

Are the sacrificed humans associated in some way:

– No

Are there self-sacrifices present:

– No

Are material offerings present:

– Yes

Notes: Material offerings noted in the cave include lengths of fabric, food like fruits (dried and fresh), and drinks like Coca-Cola. Incense is also offered to the spirit that resides in the cave, and fires are lit during rituals. Special herbs and plants may be burned/used during rituals conducted by the mganga. Students and other casual visitors to the cave may leave strips of colored/white fabric (a few inches long and perhaps an inch wide) tied to a wooden framework that stands near the pool of the spirit. The wooden frame is constructed crudely out of locally available twigs and sticks, and sits atop an archaeological deposit that consists of broken ceramics. Interestingly, many of these ceramics originate in India. It is unknown why they were brought to the cave, but it is possible that they were used to carry water and other liquids, and were broken either by accident or on purpose.

Are material offerings mandatory:

– No

Are material offerings composed of valuable objects:

– No

Are material offerings composed of daily-life objects:

– Yes

Notes: Fabric, incense, and food are all offered to the spirit of the cave.

Are material offerings interred at this place (in caches):

– Yes

Notes: There are naturally occurring "shelves" near the pool at which the spirit or Shetani is said to reside. A length of fabric is spread across one of these shelves, almost as if to make a bed for someone to rest on. On other shelves bowls with burnt incense are placed. Offerings of food and drink are also placed on these shelves. Bottles of soda must be opened for the spirit or Shetani.

Other

– Other [specify]: Food and drink offerings are present

Is attendance to worship/sacrifice mandatory:

– No

Is maintenance of the place performed:

– Yes

Notes: The local mganga performs the maintenance of the area. This includes removal of ritual artifacts once they have been used and perhaps lightly sweeping the area.

↳ Is it required:

– I don't know

↳ Is there cleansing (for the maintenance):

– I don't know

↳ Are there periodic repairs/reconstructions:

– Yes

Notes: The pool has been dredged at least once and the sediment piled to one side. No other repairs/reconstructions are known to have taken place, other than the periodic reconstruction of the wooden frame to which offerings of fabric are tied.

↳ Is the maintenance performed by permanent staff:

– No

↳ Other

– Other [specify]: None

Pilgrimage and Festivals

Are pilgrimages present:

– No

Notes: Formal pilgrimages to the cave do not exist, but people certainly travel from afar to visit the cave. There are reports of students from Dar es Salaam visiting the cave to leave offerings. Whether such visits are casual or purposeful remains unknown

Is this place a venue for feasting:

– No

Are festivals present:

– No

Divination and Healing

Is divination present:

– I don't know

Notes: The mganga is a healer, but also conducts divination rituals. It is possible that divination rituals take place in Kuumbi Cave.

Is healing present/practiced at this place:

– Yes

Notes: The mganga is primarily a healer, so the bulk of the rituals performed at Kuumbi center around healing, either of the individual or the community. The exact details of these rituals remain unknown, as they are conducted in secret.

↳ Incubation

– No

↳ Healing magic

– Yes

↳ Cleansing

– I don't know

↳ Offerings of models of body parts:

– No

↳ Expiation

– I don't know

↳ Other

–Other [specify]: none

Institutions and Scriptures

Religious Specialists

Are religious specialists present/in charge of this place:

Religious specialists are individuals whose primary duties within a population group are not concerned with subsistence or craft production but the maintenance of the religious landscape and culture of the group.

– Yes

Notes: A healer known in Kiswahili as an "mganga" (pl. "waganga") takes charge of the rituals that occur in this cave. In colonial literature, "mganga" is usually translated as "witchdoctor", but this translation has fallen out of favor. Instead, "mganga" is usually translated these days as "healer" or "divination specialist". The mganga conducts the rituals that venerate and contact the spirit of the cave.

↳ Present full time

– No

↳ Present part time

– Yes

Notes: The mganga is primarily either a fisher or a farmer in his "full-time job". He is not a religious specialist, but rather someone whose primary task is something other than the work of mganga.

↳ Are the religious specialists of specific sex/gender:

– Yes

Notes: The mganga for the most part tend to be men. However, female mganga may be present and simply unknown to scholars.

↳ Are the religious specialists of specific ethnicity:

– No

↳ Are the religious specialists of specific class/cast:

– No

↳ Are religious specialists dedicated to the place for life:

– No

↳ Are the religious specialists stratified in a hierarchical system:

– No

Does this place incorporate a living space for religious specialists:

– No

Is this place used for the training of religious specialists:

– I don't know

Notes: The extent to which the cave is necessary for the training of a new mganga is unknown.

However, an mganga takes trainees with him to observe rituals and likely learn how to perform them.

Are there formal institutions for the maintenance of the place:

Institutions that are authorized by the religious community or political leaders

– No

Bureaucracy

Is there a formal bureaucracy present at this place:

A bureaucracy consists of a hierarchical system of accounting and rule maintenance primarily concerned with material wealth.

– No

Does this place control economic resources (land, goods, tools):

– No

Public Works

Does this place serve as a location for services to the community:

– No

Writing/Scriptures

Is non-religious writing stored at this place:

Economic documents, records etc.

– No

Are there scriptures associated with this place:

– No

Bibliography

General References

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